

METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL- PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE IN FUTURE EDUCATORS BASED ON THE CULTURAL-HUMANITARIAN APPROACH

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Abstract. *The article examines the problem of forming the pedagogical culture of a kindergarten teacher, reveals the essential features of pedagogical skill, and also reveals the specifics of the teacher's professional activity.*

Keywords: *pedagogical culture, pedagogical and professional skills, personality, pedagogical position, self-regulation, thinking, pedagogical knowledge and skills.*

Reforms in the field of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan are designed to contribute to the implementation of the main tasks of socio-economic and cultural development of society in the 21st century, in the era of new educational technologies and innovations.

Since preschool education is the initial link of the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of this field, attention to the field - all areas of the person (emotional, personal, spiritual and moral) prioritizes creation of conditions that help to activate creative potential, reflect knowledge based on one's own experience.

It is important that pedagogues, parents and children, who are the main participants of the educational process, show the full potential of their personalities in this process. The teacher's personality and skills are reflected in his professional activity. In this regard, the demands placed on the pedagogue's professional and pedagogical skills and his pedagogical culture are increasing. Today's society requires future educators to have a pedagogical culture as a component of their pedagogical skills.

There are several approaches to understanding professional skills in pedagogy. First of all, pedagogical culture is required for this. Pedagogical culture, in its turn, is a part of universal culture, it unites the field of pedagogical and historical-cultural experience, regulates and determines the sphere of pedagogical interaction.

"Pedagogical culture exists in material and spiritual forms. Material forms of pedagogical culture include values and tools. Pedagogical knowledge, theories, concepts and developed pedagogical experience, professional and ethical standards of education and training collected by mankind constitute the moral values of pedagogical culture.

According to the improved "First Step" educational program: "The pedagogue who implements the state educational program respects the personality of the child and organizes the process of education and upbringing in accordance with the principles of the program. As a facilitator, a teacher uses his knowledge, skills and resources to educate and educate children. The pedagogue plans the process of education and upbringing, creates a developmental environment that contributes to the comprehensive development of the child and unlocks his potential. For this, the pedagogue knows the characteristics of the child's development, understands his feelings, identifies and takes into account the needs and interests of each child. The teacher creates such an inclusive environment in the group where every child should feel honored, capable and involved in the educational process. The teacher contributes to the development of the child's ability to act

independently, to achieve results and realize achievements, as well as to enjoy them. The teacher also helps the children to feel confident that every child can get help and encouragement from the teacher when they need it. The teacher documents, analyzes and evaluates his professional activity in order to constantly improve his professional competence. The teacher respects the opinion and experience of the child, parents and representatives of the local community and builds his work on the basis of equal partnership.”

We can observe that in the last decade, the complexity (or modernization) of interpersonal relations in society has had an impact on the professional culture of every profession in society, including educators. That is, we can take as an example the lack of communication skills in people, the inability to use the flow of information wisely in the process of globalization, the materialization of personal values, the fact that almost all pedagogues working in the field are women, and the low potential of pedagogues working in the field of preschool education. The preschool education system, which is being rebuilt, requires the development of new target instructions and methods aimed at developing the professional knowledge and skills of the pedagogue, creating conditions for him. To this day and in the future, it is important that educators have a sufficient system of knowledge in their profession and field for the practical application of the programs and methods developed for the development of the field. In order to become a skilled master of their profession, future teachers should have acquired qualities such as openness to news, creative thinking, curiosity, initiative, creativity, mechanisms and laws of the pedagogical process. This allows the future educator to think and create innovations in the field, independently analyze pedagogical phenomena, divide them into parts, understand each part in relation to the whole, and find its constituent elements.

In the process of studying the theories of education and upbringing of Western and Eastern scholars created up to this day, future educators will learn the right approach to the phenomena under consideration, adequate ideas and conclusions for their solution. they learn to find ways and solutions to optimize it.

In conclusion, we should say that when we read the opinions of many scientists who conducted research on the topic of "Pedagogical culture", an educated (educated) person is a person who is dominated by the image of humanity. The basis of pedagogical culture is humanitarianism. The high title "Pedagogue" will have its true meaning when it is inseparable from the concept of "Culture". Because culture covers all aspects of social life, any type of human activity. It embodies the way of thinking and behavior of a person, it is not limited only to the educational process - the breadth and depth of human knowledge, but also his good behavior, intelligence - the ability to clearly express himself, thinking, it means listening, being able to accept correctly, and behaving in accordance with the situation. Naturally, a high personal culture cannot be imagined without rest. Of course, it is no exaggeration to say that a high pedagogical culture is the result of a person's continuous and long work on himself. Because the great Russian scientist Ushinsky said, “A teacher lives as long as he learns, and teaching dies as soon as he stops learning”.

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